

HIVOMOT

High power and VOLTage operation of
electric MOTors in aeronautics

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Author(s):	Marco Satrustegui (CEIT), Miguel Martínez-Iturralde (CEIT) Santiago Sanz (SUPRASYS), Gustavo Sarmiento (SUPRASYS) Alex Lopez (SUPRASYS), David Gandia (SUPRASYS)
Partners contributed :	SUPRASYS, ANTEC, ALCONZA, CEIT
Reviewer:	Marco Satrustegui (CEIT)
Contact :	Marco Satrustegui (CEIT) Researcher at CEIT Paseo Mikeletegi, N° 48 20009, Donostia - San Sebastián Teléfono: (+34) 943 212800 msatrustegui@ceit.es

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report contains the initial requirements for the design of a MW-class HTS motor in terms of electromagnetic, mechanical and thermal design.

1. INTRODUCTION

Project HIVOMOT (High power and VOLTage operation of electric MOTors in aeronautics) deals with the study, conceptual design, manufacture, and test of a superconducting solution demonstrator for electric motors in planes.

In order to facilitate a progressive incorporation of high temperature superconductors (HTS) propulsion systems, additionally HIVOMOT seek a configuration able to be used in “conventional” planes, attempting to match with standards limitations in current aeronautics.

When approaching a design of an electrical machine, it is necessary to previously define different requirements (or goals) such as output power, power density, torque, etc. In addition, it is a well-known fact that depending on the application, these requirements change a lot.

To achieve an accurate motor design, it is necessary to define as precise as possible the final application together with its requirements. In this sense, this document tries to define the requirements of an electric motor for aircraft applications, more precisely, for the propulsion system of a regional aircraft.

These requirements can be classified in different groups depending on their nature. This document has been divided taking this into account, and the following groups have been identified:

- Electromagnetic requirements
- Motor topology
- Cryogenic requirements
- Auxiliary system and energy consumption limitations

2. ELECTROMAGNETIC REQUIREMENTS

2.1 Output power

The E-Fan project [1] is referenced in this call (JTI-CS2-2020-CFP11-THT-12), which pointed to a motor with a 3000 VDC electrical distribution scheme (Figure 1), in order to replace one of the four turbofan engines by a 2 MW electric motor.

Figure 1. Main features of the E-Fan-X test aircraft obtained from the call.

2.2 Rotational speed

As can be seen in Figure 2, pure electric arrangements are directly attached to the propeller [2], which leads us to rotating speeds of around 2500-4000 rpm [3].

Figure 2. Principal arrangements of components in alternative propulsion systems [2].

In addition, Jaime Fernandez (member of the EAB, from ITP) recommends setting a 2700 rpm rotation speed for a 3 m fan.

2.3 Power density and efficiency

Next table shows some of the electric motors for aircraft propulsion developed in the last years.

Table 1. Electric motor concepts developed for aircraft applications.

Project	Year	Machine type	Output power [kW]	Power density [kW/kg]	Rotational speed [rpm]	Electromagnetic efficiency [%]
SUGAR Volt [4]	2015	SRM	-	3-5	2500	92
SP260D [5]	2019	PM	260	5.9	2500	95
SP2000D [5]	2019	PM	2000	7.7	1300	-
Bi-2223 HTS wire [6], [7]	2009	HTS	1000	-	1800	97.77
NASA GRC [8]	2019	Partially superconducting	1400	16	6800	98
UTP [9]	2013	SPM	2500	14,1	13600	-
U. of Illinois [10]	2018	PM	1000	15	15000	97.4
ASUMED [11]	2018	PM-HTS	1000	20	6000	-

From Table 1 we can conclude why superconductivity has been proposed recently in several projects as an enabling technology for lighter and more compact electrical motors. The main competitor for superconducting technology seems to be the Permanent Magnets (PM). Taking into account that the electrical machine proposed in [8] is a conceptual design and that machines in [9], [10] work at much higher rotational speeds (13600 and 15000 rpm, respectively), the following goals are proposed:

- Power density: between 7.7 kW/kg and 15 kW/kg
- Overall efficiency (cooling system included) : ≥ 95 % (at nominal conditions)

2.4 Power converter requirements

For a proper design of an electric motor, it is vital to determine the main features of its controller (power converter).

One of the key parameters for the design of electric motors is the switching frequency, which is constantly increasing as the technology related to semiconductors evolves. An initial value of 30 kHz seems reasonable looking at some of the latest research in this field [12], [13].

In addition, there are more parameters of interest for the design of the electric motor, such as:

- The switching strategy (E.g. SV-PWM, etc.)
- Maximum phase current of the converter (A).
- Maximum phase voltage of the converter (V).
- Voltage variation over time dV/dt (kV/s)

Therefore, the parameters shown in Table 2 are defined regarding the power electronics governing the electric motor. V_{DC} parameter is an established requirement in the call, and HIVOMOT will study solutions to such high voltage in altitude.

Table 2. Main features of the power converter.

Parameter	Value	Units
V_{DC}	3000	V
Switching frequency	30	kHz

2.5 Summary

To sum up, Table 3 shows the electromagnetic requirements defined previously.

Table 3. Electromagnetic requirements

Parameter	Value	Units
Output power	2	MW
Rotational speed	2700	rpm
Efficiency	>95	%
Power density	7.7-15	kW/kg
V_{DC}	3000	V
Switching frequency	30	kHz

3. VOLUME REQUIREMENTS

The electric motor must be designed according to some specific volume/dimension limitations. So, as this topic is focused on the E-Fan project, the volume requirements will be oriented to regional aircraft topologies. In this sense, the volume requirements will be dependent on the nacelle and fan dimensions.

3.1 Propulsion in regional aircrafts

To delimit the electric motor external dimensions (diameter and length), special attention should be paid on the nacelle and fan characteristics. In this sense, there are two kind of propulsion systems, a ducted fan or a propeller (as depicted in Figure 3).

Figure 3. Different shaft power consumption [14].

Regardless of the propulsion system, the nacelle can be defined by some global dimensions, which are depicted in the next figure.

Figure 4. Nacelle cross section with global dimensions in a ducted fan [15].

In addition, as can be seen in Figure 5, the electric motor is usually embedded within the nacelle and the main reason resides in the necessity of protecting the electric motor against aerodynamic forces arising from the fan.

Figure 5. Hybrid propulsion system proposed by [16].

With these constraints in mind, the propulsion system should be designed according to three key parameters:

- The fan diameter (D_{FAN}).
- The diameter of the spinner (D_{SPIN})
- The length of the nacelle (L_{NAC})

3.1.1. Fan diameter

As it is stated in [17], the next figure shows different fan diameters for regional aircrafts.

Figure 6. Relationship between fan diameters and take-off thrust [17].

In addition, [15] proposes a D_{FAN} of 3.3 m for a mid-to-long-range aircraft as a reference value for his study. Therefore, a fan diameter of 3 m seems reasonable for a regional aircraft.

3.1.2. Spinner diameter

The nacelle is usually limited by the maximum diameter of the spinner, as can be seen in the next picture.

Figure 7. Engine and nacelle dimensions of ATR72-500 [18].

The spinner’s diameter is usually between 20-30% of the fan diameter (D_{FAN}). Therefore, taking the D_{FAN} value of 3 m as a reference, the spinner diameter could be set between 0.6-0.9 m.

3.1.3. Nacelle length (required space for electric motor)

The length of the nacelle can be defined from either, the fan diameter to length ratio (L_{NAC}/D_{FAN}) or the spinner diameter to length ratio (L_{NAC}/D_{SPIN}) based on previous research. In this regard, the following table resumes the research found on this topic.

Table 4. Different nacelle dispositions from literature.

Reference	Year	L_{NAC}/D_{FAN}	L_{NAC} [m]
Mahieu [18]	2016	-	3.3
Majic [15]	2016	1.6	-
GTF-11 nacelle [17]	2012	0.7	-
Chiesa [19]	2016	0.46	0.88
Biser [20]	2020	-	1

In addition, [20] shows different motor displacement within the nacelle, as can be seen in the next picture.

Figure 8. Visualized nacelle geometry for different nacelle diameters [20].

So, from the previous information and looking at Figure 8, an available nacelle length (L_{NAC}) of 1 m is considered.

3.2 Electric motor dimensions

In the previous section, the main dimensions of the propulsion system in a regional aircraft were defined and are summarized in the next table.

Table 5. Main dimensions of the propulsion system in a regional aircraft.

Parameter	Value [m]
Fan diameter	3
Spinner diameter	0.6-0.9
Nacelle length	1

Considering these dimensions, as the electric motor will be embedded in this system, as can be seen in Figure 9. The following dimensions are proposed for the design:

- Maximum electric motor external diameter = 0.9 m
- Maximum length for the propulsion system = 1 m
- Electric motor weight = 130 – 260 kg

Figure 9. Full turboelectric propulsion system TE4 [18].

4. HTS MOTOR TOPOLOGY

One of the most important decisions to be taken when an HTS motor needs to be designed is whether the machine will be partially or fully superconductor. That means that the two components in the motor (rotor and stator in a rotary machine) can, in theory, be superconducting. The compacity of this topology fully superconducting will be maximum.

However, there are practical reasons hindering the selection a fully superconducting machine. The AC losses in the inductive part, which is typically the stator. AC losses in a superconductor penalty the heat load and therefore the cryogenics.

Secondly the study in HIVOMOT of the high voltage in the stator. In a HTS stator the use of high voltage is not necessary.

Thirdly, the time to reach the market. HIVOMOT consortium considers the strategy of reduced innovations in a new technology, trying to fit it to standards. Therefore, HIVOMOT solution intends to be an intermediate step.

The selection of synchronous motor topology has the advantage to work the field winding in DC, avoiding the AC superconductor losses, at least in a first approximation (AC ripples over the DC signal can cause still some AC losses, despite they are usually negligible).

Table 6. Preliminary motor topology

Type of motor	Partially superconducting synchronous machine
Superconducting part	DC Field windings
Superconducting material	Superconducting wires (2G HTS or MgB2)
Cryogenic parts	Preliminary Internal rotor (cryogenic rotary joint) or external stator (split rings and brushes)

5. CRYOGENIC COOLING SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

Figure 10. Cryogenic cooling system scheme with cryocoolers and rotating SC windings

Figure 11. Cryogenic cooling scheme with LH₂ tank and static SC windings

Table 7. Preliminary cryogenic operational goals for HIVOMOT

Cold mass	TBD kg
Working temperature	20-25 K
Working pressure	0.1 – 2 MPa
Working cryogen	GHe
Cryogenic system	Stationary cryocooler or LH2 heat exchanger with working fluid circulation.
Thermal insulation system	Actively cooled radiation shield at around 77 K
Cooling power	40-60 W at 20 K 200 - 300 W at 77 K
Working fluid mass flow	TBD

6. AUXILIAR SYSTEMS AND ENERGY CONSUMPTION LIMITATIONS

HIVOMOT will require a definition of important issues as the motor configuration or superconductor and cryogenics selection. Understanding this section as a frame to try to fulfil, following features are considered as more important.

6.1 AUXILIAR SYSTEMS

Specific cryogenic conditions for HIVOMOT are not still fixed. However, in general terms a HTS motor requires a thermal environment which is kept fundamentally by a cryostat, a vacuum system and a thermal sink. The last ones are considered as auxiliary systems.

Despite the efforts to define lightweight cryostat, this system increments the weight of the motor. With regards the vacuum system, it may require a pump and vacuum lines that keep the vacuum grade periodically. And finally, the thermal sink may require a cryogen, a deposit and a cooling system that recirculate and cool down it again, and a chiller to refrigerate associated compressors, despite air cooling systems could be an alternative.

Table 8 presents the weight and power consumption of the typical auxiliary systems for a superconducting motor in other power applications. Such systems are necessary to keep the vacuum and cryogenic conditions. The specific application for aircrafts requires to optimize or even include new vacuum and cryogenic solutions, compatible with the weight and volume restrictions.

In terms of weight relation to the motor, following the power density target (>7.7 kW/kg), HIVOMOT aims to limit the weight of the 2 MW motor to around 260 kg. However, the weight of the auxiliary systems can be greater than the motor itself. This auxiliary system can refrigerated several motors, and that the scalability rate is smaller for auxiliaries, and that there is room of improvement. Such studies will be done in WP2.

Preliminarily, a target for cryogenic heat leaks in a 2 MW SC motor has been established in Table 7. However due to the limitation in efficiency at cryogenic temperatures (less than 1%) means that required power consumption is huge in comparison.

Table 8. Weight and power consumption of auxiliary systems for SC parts

	Weight (kg)	% Weight	Estimated Power Consumption (kW)	% Power consumption
Cryogenic systems	172,9	14%	0,9	3%
Cryogenics lines	253,3	31%	-	
Vacuum systems	96,3	8%	3,2	11%
Chiller systems	590,0	47%	24,0	85%
Total	1112,5	100%	28,1	100%

As pointed before, another important objective of the project is to define cryogenic systems and their auxiliaries, trying to reduce the weight (and also the volume) impact inside the aircraft. Despite this HTS technology is recent and the conventional plane may require some modifications to host it, a good procedure to follow is to try to adapt the new technology to the limitations of current aviation procedures.

Therefore, the auxiliary systems should follow:

- Weight limitation in the current auxiliary systems (TBD)
- Plane location of auxiliary systems and deposits (TBD)
- Pressure vessel rules inside a plane, for instance limitation to pressure, time to recharge and related conditions (TBD).
- Others (TBD)

6.2 ENERGY CONSUMPTION LIMITATIONS

Following Table 8, it is straightforward to estimate the impact of auxiliary systems in the overall efficiency of a 2 MW motor. It is the limiting situation in which only one 2 MW HTS motor drives the plane, the cryogenics systems and auxiliaries deduct less than 2% of efficiency. In this project this percentage should be maintained.

However, the very first rough estimation of a consumption of 28.1 kW for the cryogenics and auxiliaries should be compatible with current figure of generation onboards. Therefore, the study of the energy consumption in comparison with the generation on-board should be considered in WP2.

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